

A comprehensive study on the applicability of kernel ridge regression for predicting atomization energies

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ABSTRACT

Motivated by the previous study by Rupp *et al.* [Phys. Rev. Lett, 108, 058301], we implement an improved Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR) model trained on the QM7 dataset and provide a comprehensive evaluation of its applicability. The model is further applied to predict the stability difference between the *cis*- and *trans*-isomers of 1,2-dichloroethylene. The accuracy of our model is comparable to that of density functional theory (DFT) calculations, achieving a mean absolute error (MAE) of approximately 4.4 kcal/mol on QM7 dataset. Our findings suggest that, although the KRR model is well established, its performance and transferability can be substantially enhanced through careful feature engineering.

KEYWORDS: Machine learning, Artificial intelligence (AI), Molecular representation, Computational chemistry

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, computational quantum chemistry and condensed matter physics have achieved remarkable progress. The computational methods in this field are not limited to small molecules but extended to technologically important materials, including Li-ion batteries.¹ Such advances have been enabled not only by improvements in computing hardware but also by significant developments in simulation algorithms. These algorithms span a wide range of theoretical frameworks, from mean-field-based approaches, such as Hartree–Fock (HF), density functional theory (DFT), and DFT+*U*,² to quantum many-body methods, configuration interaction (CI), coupled-cluster (CC) theory, and dynamical mean-field theory (DMFT).^{3,4}

Despite these advances, fundamental challenges remain in obtaining accurate solutions and predicting the properties of quantum systems, particularly for correlated materials and excited-state phenomena. Many computational approaches suffer from limited accuracy and/or exponentially increasing computational cost when applied to such systems. To address these limitations, machine learning (ML) techniques have increasingly been incorporated into computational chemistry and materials science.⁵ These approaches offer the potential to overcome several inherent constraints of conventional methods.

In this work, we present possible improvements to a simple machine-learning model, namely Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR), and apply it to a chemically subtle problem: the *cis* effect in 1,2-dichloroethylene. Our study examines the inherent limitations of the model and proposes strategies to enhance its performance and transferability.

This paper is organized as follows: In Sec. 2, we briefly review the Kernel Ridge model, on which our improved dataset and feature vectors are applied. In Sec. 3, we present our main results showing the importance of feature vector selection. We also present the result on chemically subtle issue, namely *cis* effect. The conclusion is given in Sec. 4.

2. METHOD AND THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Model

While deep neural networks represent state-of-the-art AI models, their major limitation is the requirement for extremely large datasets. In contrast, ridge-based models have been widely used when only a limited size of training set is available, like other classical ML approaches, e.g., decision-tree. In this perspective, KRR model is employed to predict the atomization energy, extending previous applications by improving its accuracy to address a chemically subtle problem.

Our models follow the KRR framework described in a work by Rupp *et al.*⁶ The mathematical notations in this paper follow their work. The feature vector, say Coulomb matrix M , is modified to improve model accuracy. Also, we adopted the Δ -learning technique by introducing baseline model⁷. To prevent overfitting, we use randomly selected 1500 molecules as the test set. The hyperparameters λ and σ were optimized by minimizing the mean absolute error (MAE) on the test set. The optimal values of λ and σ depend not only on the composition of the training set but also on the choice of feature vectors used. We also note that while our results are based on a single randomly selected train-test split, our main results are robust to the choice of train-test split. With 10 repeated random splits, we found that the standard deviation of the MAE is only 0.31 kcal/mol, 0.21 kcal/mol, and 0.11 kcal/mol for the models introduced below, namely models based on bare nuclear charge Z , effective nuclear charge Z_{eff} , and general feature vectors.

2.2 Data set

The QM7 dataset is a subset of GDB-13,⁸ decorated by Coulomb matrices representing molecular structures, along with their atomization energies computed within the DFT level calculations. The data set contains 7165 molecules up to 23 atoms, including 7 heavy atoms C, N, O, and S with the Coulomb matrix defined based on the nuclear charges of atoms in each molecule. To investigate transferability of the dataset and the model, we choose 1,2-dichloroethylene as our target molecule. Because the QM7 dataset contains no chlorine atoms, we expanded the dataset by adding additional Cl-containing molecules.

2.3 Model improvement

The KRR model trained solely on the Coulomb matrix is known to achieve a MAE of 9.9 kcal/mol on the QM7 dataset.⁶ To improve this model, we carefully engineer the feature vector in three-folds.

Firstly, we modified the Coulomb matrix by replacing the bare nuclear charge Z with more chemically sound quantities, the effective nuclear charge Z_{eff} . This modification yields noticeable improvements in prediction accuracy by incorporating more realistic electronic environments.

Secondly, we augmented the feature vector with additional molecular descriptors. While modern AI-based approaches use thousands of descriptors,^{9,10} we adopted a selected set of them, including connectivity, compositions, bond lengths and angle distributions, and coordination numbers. The fingerprint considered in this study is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Summary of the 39 molecular descriptors.

Feature group	Number of features	Description
Distance Statistics	4	Mean, standard deviation, median of all-to-all interatomic distance (r_{ij}), and Shannon entropy $-\sum_{ij} r_{ij} \log(r_{ij})$ of the distance distribution.
Radial Distribution	8	Normalized histogram of r_{ij} as a function of distance. (Range: 0–10 Bohr, 8 bins with bin width: 1.25 Bohr).
Bond length Statistics	6	Number of short bonds (< 3 Bohr), Number of medium bonds (3 – 5 Bohr), and statistics of bonds (mean, standard deviation, min, max).
Atomic Composition	6	Number of specific elements, N_Z with $Z \in \{\text{H, C, N, O, S, Cl}\}$ in a given molecule
Coordination	4	Statistics (mean, standard deviation, min, and max) of the number of neighbors for each atom in the molecule.
Bond Angles	4	Statistics (mean, standard deviation, min, and max) of angles θ_{ijk} for connected atoms i, j , and k .
Connectivity	2	Total number of bonds, N_b (cutoff < 4.0 Bohr) and ratio between N_b and possible bonds, $N_{atom}(N_{atom} - 1)/2$.
Torsion & Planarity	3	Max and mean value of dihedral angles and planarity deviation around C=C bonds.
Geometric Strain	2	Harmonic strain: $\sum_b (r - r_0)^2$ for bonds and $\sum_a (\theta - \theta_0)^2$ for angles. The ideal bond length r_0 (Bohr) is defined based on atomic pairs: (C,H): 2.0, (C,C): 2.9, (C,N): 2.8, (C,O): 2.7, (N,H): 1.9, (O,H): 1.8, and (C,Cl): 3.3. An ideal bond angle $\theta_0 = 109.5^\circ$ is used for all sp^3 -hybridized atoms.

To ensure consistent scaling across heterogeneous features, each descriptor x_j was normalized by the group-specific weight w_g :

$$w_g^2 = \frac{1}{N_{train}} \frac{1}{N_g} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{train}} \sum_{j \in g} x_{ij}^2 \quad (1)$$

Here, N_{train} is the number of items in the training set, N_g is the number of features in group g .

At last, we adopted a Δ -learning technique to improve model accuracy.⁷ Without Δ -learning, the model's extrapolation performance was largely limited. The baseline is determined by a simple pre-processing model; namely an atomic linear regression:⁷

$$E_{base}(M) = \sum_Z w_Z N_Z(M). \quad (2)$$

Here, $Z \in \{1, 6, 7, 8, 16, 17\}$ runs over the atomic numbers included in the dataset, representing H, C, N, O, S, and Cl, respectively. $N_Z(M)$ denotes the number of atoms Z in molecule M , and w_Z are parameters fitted to the training set. Using this baseline, our KRR models were trained to predict the residual $\Delta(M) = E_{AE}(M) - E_{base}(M)$, rather than the bare atomization energy $E_{AE}(M)$ of molecule M .

2.3 Computational details for DFT

Density functional theory (DFT) is a method for calculating the electronic structure of atoms, molecules, and their interactions at the quantum level. DFT calculations are based on electron density functions, instead of directly solving the Schrödinger equation of the many-body system of interacting electrons. The very basic idea is representing the electron-electron interaction energy E_{int} by a functional of the electron density:

$$E_{int}[n(r)] = E_{Hartree}[n(r)] + E_{xc}[n(r)] \quad (3)$$

Here, $E_{Hartree}$, E_{xc} , and $n(r)$ are the Hartree energy, the exchange-correlation energy and the electron density function, respectively.

We performed DFT calculation using the pySCF python package.^{11,12} The DFT calculations were performed within PBE0 hybrid functional,¹³ which was used to construct QM7. We also select little expensive basis set, namely def2-TZVP, to keep consistency with the original QM7 dataset. Our computational setting well reproduces the atomization energy of randomly selected 50 molecules from QM7 dataset within a MAE of ~ 4.25 kcal/mol. We note that the atomization energy in the QM7 dataset, calculated by FHI-aims code with tier-2 basis set has comparable error < 5 kcal/mol for thermo-chemistry data.^{6,14}

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Bare atomic number Z feature

To reproduce the previous results, we first follow the same methodology, but feature normalization was made. Fig. 1(a) shows the relative distance between the molecules in the training set. The distribution clearly matches that obtained in the previous work, only normalized feature space, for instance, it shows two main-peak structure with one small distance and a few molecule pairs with

larger distances.⁶ Fig. 1(b) shows atomization energy predicted by the model, compared with the exact atomization energy. The MAE of ~ 10.14 kcal/mol is consistent with the previously reported value, confirming that our model well reproduces the previous results.

The molecule with the largest absolute error ($=94.65$ kcal/mol) is *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF). The reason for this large error might be attributed to the relatively large distance from its neighbours in the feature space.

Figure 1 (a) Pair-wise distance between molecules in QM7 dataset. The distance is normalized by the standard deviation of the length of feature vectors (Euclidian norm of eigenvalues of Coulomb matrix) (b) correlation plot of atomization energy between true (DFT-PBE0) and predicted result by KKR model.

3.2 Improved models

Using the effective nuclear charge as the basis for the Coulomb matrix reduces the MAE to 8.83 kcal/mol, corresponding to roughly a 13% improvement. More importantly, the large prediction error for molecule DMF decreases dramatically, from 94.65 kcal/mol to 45.01 kcal/mol. Because Z_{eff} incorporates the effect of core electrons, it provides a more chemically realistic representation, which likely explains this improvement.

Encouraged by this improvement, we further expanded the feature vector by introducing 39 additional molecular fingerprints. The resulting generalized feature vector consists of 62 components (39 fingerprints + 23 effective charge-based features).

This extended representation further improves the model accuracy, yielding a MAE of 4.44 kcal/mol. Such a low error is unlikely to be achieved using the original Z -only Coulomb matrix. Previous work estimated that even with an infinitely large training set, the MAE of the Z -only representation would saturate near 7.6 kcal/mol.⁶ We also note in passing that the MAE of our KRR model is comparable with that of more sophisticated ML models, 3.0 kcal/mol,¹⁵ or 3.6 kcal/mol.¹⁶ More interestingly the absolute error of DMF is surprisingly reduced to 5.13 kcal/mol.

Fig. 2 summarizes the error distributions for the three feature sets. It is clearly shown that feature vectors incorporating general fingerprints outperform the other models, showing lower absolute errors.

Figure 2 Absolute error $|E_{AE}^{pred}(M) - E_{AE}^{true}(M)|$ of atomization energies for each molecule. The predicted values are obtained from three different models, using bare atomic number Z (blue), effective nuclear charge (orange), and effective nuclear charge with general fingerprints (green).

3.3 *cis* effect of 1,2-dichloroethylene

Having established the accuracy of our model for atomization energies, we now apply it to the stability difference between the *cis*- and *trans*-isomers of 1,2-dichloroethylene. Although *trans*-isomers are generally more stable than *cis*-isomers, 1,2-dichloroethylene is a well-known exception.^{17,18}

First, we performed DFT calculations using different basis sets. To keep the consistency of the methods with QM7 data, we focused in PBE0 functional. In the previous calculation results, it was shown that the relative energy difference between *cis*- and *trans*- isomer is distributing from 0.38 kcal/mol (B3LYP) to 3.35 kcal/mol (MP2),¹⁸ depending on the underlying DFT functional. Table 2 summarizes the computed atomization energies for both isomers. Although the absolute atomization energies depend strongly on the basis set, the relative energy difference ΔE is reasonably consistent, except for the minimal basis set, STO-3G. This provides a reasonable DFT-level reference for subsequent machine-learning-based prediction.

Table 2 Calculated atomization energies of *cis*- and *trans*-1,2-dichloroethylene in kcal/mol. PBE0 hybrid functional is adopted with various basis choices. In all different basis one can see the *cis* effect. ΔE denotes the energy difference between *cis*- and *trans*-1,2-dichloroethylene using the corresponding basis sets.

	STO-3G	cc-pVTZ	def2-SVP	def2-TZVP
<i>cis</i>	-588.93	-525.55	-528.86	-527.03
<i>trans</i>	-589.48	-525.13	-528.30	-526.54
ΔE	0.55	-0.42	-0.56	-0.49

Next, we applied the machine learning models. Note that the energy difference between the two isomers equals the difference of the atomization energy of them:

$$\Delta E = (E_{\text{cis}} - E_{\text{atom}}) - (E_{\text{trans}} - E_{\text{atom}}), \quad (4)$$

where $E_{\text{atom}} = 2E(\text{C}) + 2E(\text{H}) + 2E(\text{Cl})$ is the same for both isomers.

Because the original QM7 dataset does not contain chlorine, the models trained on the dataset fail to capture the correct relative stability. For instance, the model using general fingerprints incorrectly predicts an atomization energy of -444.78 kcal/mol for both isomers. This breakdown in the predictive accuracy is not surprising, given the absence of Cl-containing molecules in the training set. In fact, the closest neighbourhood in the QM7 feature space is isothiazole-3-carbaldehyde ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_3\text{NOS}$) with the atomization energy of -1115.57 kcal/mol, far from the reference energy of *trans*-1,2-dichloroethylene, -527.03 kcal/mol, obtained from the DFT result.

To overcome this limitation, we extended the dataset by adding Cl-containing molecules into the dataset. We have prepared three different level of datasets, namely, QM7-Cl-100, QM7-Cl-500, and QM7-Cl-1k with 100, 500, and 1000 Cl-containing molecules added to the original QM7 dataset to construct these extended datasets, respectively. We note that the target molecule, 1,2-dichloroethylene, was explicitly excluded from all these datasets.

Table 3 summarizes the predicted atomization energies and the resulting energy differences between the isomers for each model and data set size. Once a sufficient number of Cl-containing molecules are included in the training set (approximately 1,000), all three models converge and reasonably reproduce both the atomization energies and the relative stability of the *cis* isomer. For instance, all three models reproduce the negative sign of ΔE , with errors within approximately 4-6 kcal/mol. However, as the number of Cl-containing molecules decreases, the Coulomb-matrix-based models deteriorate rapidly, particularly for the *trans*-isomer, whereas the model incorporating general molecular features continues to provide stable and reliable predictions for both isomers. These observations clearly support our central claim that feature engineering is as crucial as the model architecture itself.

Table 3 Predicted atomization energy of *cis*- and *trans*-1,2-dichloroethylene (kcal/mol). The KRR model with general fingerprints shows accurately predict *cis* effect and reasonable atomization energy of both isomers. Coulomb-matrix-only models, however, fail to predict the unstable *trans*-isomer when the number of data is not sufficient.

Model	Datasets	<i>cis</i> -	<i>trans</i> -	ΔE
Z	QM7-100	-528.46	-501.90	+26.55
	QM7-500	-535.74	-505.21	+30.53
	QM7-1k	-534.69	-541.07	-6.38
Z_{eff}	QM7-100	-528.61	-504.36	+24.25
	QM7-500	-532.31	-505.51	+26.80
	QM7-1k	-535.17	-537.87	-2.71
General	QM7-100	-528.38	-535.71	-7.33
	QM7-500	-533.98	-539.44	-5.46
	QM7-1k	-534.12	-538.93	-4.81

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we investigated the applicability and transferability of the KRR model for predicting molecular atomization energies. Unlike many modern machine-learning or AI approaches that require tons of training datasets, complex architectures, and/or high-dimensional descriptors, the KRR framework remains attractive due to its intuitive formalism and its ability to perform well even with relatively small datasets. Similar kernel-based approaches have also been successfully applied in other fields, such as analytic continuation in many-body physics.

Our results demonstrate that the performance of the KRR model depends on the choice of feature representation, not only on the dimensionality of the features but also on their chemical relevance. Modifying the Coulomb matrix by incorporating effective nuclear charges significantly improves predictive accuracy compared with using bare atomic numbers.

Furthermore, the use of additional molecular fingerprints enhances both the accuracy and the extendibility of the model, enabling better generalization to chemical species not present in the original QM7 dataset. These findings highlight the crucial role of feature engineering in improving the robustness and transferability of kernel-based machine-learning models for computational chemistry.

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Author Contributions

S.L. and T.H.P. conducted the model construction and performed the result analysis. H.K., T.M.E.J., T.X.Y., and S.K. contributed to data generation and DFT calculations. J.S. and A.G. managed the overall project. All authors contributed to the drafting and revision of the manuscript.

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